

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ERGONOMICS: THE POSSIBILITIES OF AI, ZKP AND ML

Dziatkovskii A.

*Ph.D in Education (Artificial Intelligence /
Zero Knowledge Proof / Blockchain / Data Science)*

CEO Platinum VC & Incubator Australia

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Abstract

The directions of changes in ergonomics, which accompany the inclusion of artificial intelligence in the "human-machine" system, are considered. The problems of "weak" and "strong" artificial intelligence in ergonomics are presented.

Keywords: ergonomics, artificial intelligence, Zero-knowledge proof, problems.

Ergonomics studies the system "man-machine-environment", the interaction of man with the world, which is mediated by machinery and technology. In the 21st century this system is undergoing a major transformation. Technogenic environments include artificial intelligence and global communication information networks. A distinction is made between weak and strong artificial intelligence. A strong artificial intelligence is a machine capable of thinking, being aware of itself, learning something new. Weak artificial intelligence (narrow) are programs that perform routine human functions (translation, image recognition, calculations). Will strong intelligence ever be created and when will it surpass humans?

While there seems to be time before the development of strong intelligence, weak intelligence is already firmly established in our lives and helps to automate the actions traditionally performed by humans [1]. As the digital environment is created, so is the human being. He is actively creating a digital environment. The picture of cognitive processes in the "man-machine" system is being reconsidered, in which the brain as an instrument of cognition and the machine performing the routine cognitive functions of man are seen in a reciprocal relationship. The line between the subject and the object is erased. The line between "internal" and "external" intelligence is erased. The cognitive subject is embedded in an environment of artificial intelligence, which optimizes brain activity. Ongoing processes of continuous updating, operational control and correction of parameters of the technical part of the system change human mental functions and simultaneously exist independently of him. Intelligence loses its specificity of a purely human property.

The object of study of classical ergonomics is also changing. It becomes interdisciplinary, includes all forms of human interaction with the world, which are mediated by technology and technology, to create effective ergonomic systems [4].

Neoclassical ergonomics included engineering psychology and studied complex man-made environments endowed with artificial intelligence and global communication information networks as self-developing systems. Holistic approach in such a system began

to consider a person as a subject that is actively embedded in the environment, forming a unified cognitive system. The line between subject and object, internal and external intelligence is blurred.

Mental functions are seen as embodied in the human body and, at the same time, as existing independent entities. Intellect becomes an emergent property of the whole complex system. It is likely that in the near future it will be impossible to imagine the ergonomics of work without the participation of artificial intelligence, which will control the process from beginning to end.

Today, the development of artificial intelligence is associated with the development and adaptation of AI products and services for a large range of applications [5].

If the center of natural intelligence is consciousness transforming the world, then artificial intelligence is a program, an algorithm, situational control of the world, and hybrid intelligence is a mutual adaptation of natural and artificial intelligences, their symbiosis.

Hybrid intelligence reflects the results of selection and application by the self-organizing system of effective ways to achieve the goal in an organized environment. The purpose of the whole system is to ensure the comfort, safety and efficiency of automated workplaces of labor subjects [2,3].

It is believed that modern ergonomics, uniting with many related sciences, is transformed in three directions:

physical, based on a detailed analysis of anthropometric, physiological, psychophysical, hygienic properties of the human body and their involvement in creating optimal working conditions;

cognitive, based on the models of human work with artificial intelligence through mental processes: memory, thinking, attention, speech, perception;

organizational, guaranteeing the quality and reliability of the results of hybrid intelligence, goods and services.

Of course, modern ergonomics fundamentally changes the attitude to labor, the ways of its organization and improvement. The traditional tasks of ergo-

nomics are also changing. As digital transformation intensifies, new formats of communication emerge to solve a whole range of problems, new ethical problems - and there are options for solving them.

For example, the problem associated with depersonalization and data storage mechanisms. Today artificial intelligence has acquired a powerful assistant in the form of Zero Knowledge Proof, the tasks of storing anonymous information in a secure state data system are set [3].

AI can quickly find grammatical, punctuation and semantic errors in the text. This saves up to 20% of the teacher's time. In general, AI is effective wherever you can standardize. But what about ethical problems? Gagle analyzes students' email correspondence and social media activity and informs school administrators of potential safety hazards. Surveillance? Distrust? And psychological discomfort is one of the indicators of failed ergonomics.

Excessive "digitization" of educational activity can lead to certain threats and challenges. Multisubject relations will be destroyed. There will be collisions of individuality, uniqueness, on the one hand, and the conveyor belt, on the other. Threats of discrimination against citizens and organizations will arise due to the possible presence of biases in the algorithms, intentionally or unconsciously introduced by the developers. At the same time, it is extremely difficult to detect AI errors and even more so to appeal against them, because access to such systems by outside experts is closed. The problem of incorrect interpretation of data by artificial intelligence and "raw" its algorithms remains [6,7].

Ergonomics offers an evaluation of AI systems by independent experts, the presence of warnings about the use of AI, the availability of a backup plan in case of failures and other unforeseen situations. At the same time, the regulation of technical processes in the field of AI at the level of laws and regulations may negatively affect the development of the market, while protecting citizens and organizations from the negative consequences of its use will not increase.

Strong intelligence raises even more questions. These are mostly ethical questions. Will AI be able to resolve moral issues in a situation of choice? Can autonomous weapons be created? Will the AI be offended? feel hurt? lonely? And who will control it? What could go wrong? [8]

Conclusions. Artificial intelligence issues are poorly developed in terms of ergonomics. We will rely on machine learning more and more, we will have good

intentions. AI improves human performance and efficiency. AI is necessary in critical situations to reduce casualties. But there remain issues of psychological comfort, trust, safety, and ethics, which are difficult to formalize and differ from country to country. We cannot always fully rely on AI's judgment. After all, it can be "poisoned," used for inhumane purposes. There is a lot of work ahead and new challenges.

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